

Cea Salazar VI, Boender AJ, Seelke AMH, Gaard L, Mederos SL, Rogers S, Gutierrez XZ, Bales KL, Young LJ, Trainor BC. CRISPR-mediated knockdown of oxytocin receptor in extended amygdala reduces stress-induced social avoidance in female California mice. *Horm Behav.* 2025 Nov;176:105845. doi: 10.1016/j.yhbeh.2025.105845. Epub 2025 Oct 28. PMID: 41151122.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52

53
54 CRISPR-mediated knockdown of oxytocin receptor in extended amygdala reduces stress-induced social
55 avoidance in female California mice
56
57

58 Valentina I. Cea Salazara^a, Arjen J. Boender^{b,c}, Adele M. H. Seelke^d, Liam Gaard^d, Sabrina L. Mederos^e, Sophia
59 Rogers^d, Xiomara Z. Gutierrez^d, Karen L. Bales^{d,f}, Larry J. Young^{g,h,i}, Brian C. Trainor^{a,c,e}
60

61 ^aNeuroscience Graduate Group, University of California, Davis, USA

62 ^bAchucarro Basque Center for Neuroscience, Leioa, Spain

63 ^cIkerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, Bilbao, Spain

64 ^dDepartment of Psychology, University of California, Davis, USA

65 ^eAnimal Behavior Graduate Group, University of California, Davis, USA

66 ^fDepartment of Neurobiology, Physiology, and Behavior, University of California, Davis, USA

67 ^gEmory National Primate Research Center, Emory University, Atlanta, GA, USA

68 ^hCenter for Translational Social Neuroscience, Emory University, Atlanta, GA, USA

69 ⁱDepartment of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences, Emory University School of Medicine, Atlanta, GA,
70 USA

71
72
73
74 Correspondence: bctrainor@ucdavis.edu

75 **Abstract**

76
77 Oxytocin receptors (OTRs) within the extended amygdala and nucleus accumbens (NAc) have been
78 implicated in modulating social behaviors, particularly following stress. The effects of OTR could be mediated
79 by modulating the activity of pre-synaptic axon terminals or via receptors in post-synaptic neurons or glia.
80 Using a viral-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing system in female California mice (*Peromyscus californicus*),
81 we selectively knocked down OTR in the anteromedial bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BNST) or NAc to
82 examine their roles modulating social approach and vigilance behaviors. Knockdown of OTR in the BNST
83 attenuated stress-induced decreases of social approach and had less robust effects on vigilance when
84 interacting with a target mouse behind a wire barrier. In this large arena, where mice could control their
85 proximity to a target mouse, BNST OTR knockdown also increased investigation of a non-social stimulus
86 (empty cage). Behavioral effects of BNST OTR knockdown were weaker in the small arena where focal mice
87 physically interacted with target mice. Interestingly, OTR knockdown in the NAc, reduced stress-induced social
88 vigilance without affecting social approach. These effects could mediate altered encoding of socially aversive
89 experiences, as knockdown manipulations were performed before stress exposure. Together, these results
90 highlight effects of local OTR on social behavior that are region-specific.

91

1 Introduction

Individuals affected by anxiety disorders experience significant distress in social situations that can lead to self-isolation and avoidance behaviors (Abramowitz & Deacon, 2010). Women are twice as likely to develop anxiety disorders compared to men (Kessler et al., 2012). While there are existing pharmaceutical and behavioral therapeutic interventions, ~40% do not respond to these treatments (Williams & Trainor, 2018). Oxytocin is a neuropeptide that modulates social and emotional behaviors (Gimpl & Fahrenholz, 2001) and has been considered as a potential alternative therapeutic to existing antidepressants (MacDonald & Feifel, 2013 and 2014; Modi & Young., 2012; Gutkowska & Jankowski, 2012; Giovanna et al., 2020; van Zuiden et al., 2017; Schultebrasucks et al., 2022; Rashidi et al., 2025). However, the field has struggled to explain findings where intranasal oxytocin sometimes decreases anxiety symptoms but in other cases increases anxiety and other psychiatric symptoms (Tabak et al., 2022; Schultebrasucks et al., 2022). A potential explanation for these results is the social salience hypothesis of oxytocin (Bartz et al., 2011; Shamay-Tsoory & Abu-Akel, 2016), which proposes that oxytocin can modulate behaviors by enhancing attention to both positive and negative social contexts. Several lines of evidence indicate that oxytocin promotes salience by acting in discrete neural circuits to drive these dynamic responses (Steinman et al., 2016, 2019a; Nasanbuyan et al., 2018; Osakada et al. 2024; Duque-Wilckens et al., 2018).

In appetitive social contexts, activation of oxytocin receptors (OTR) in the mesolimbic dopamine system play a key role in promoting social approach behaviors. The nucleus accumbens (NAc) modulates motivational and learning processes (Salgado & Kaplitt, 2015), and activation of OTR within the NAc facilitates social approach (Williams et al., 2020), social learning (Nardou et al., 2019), pair bonding (Liu & Wang, 2003; Rigney et al., 2025), and social novelty seeking (Smith et al., 2017). Activation of OTR in the ventral tegmental area (VTA) has also been found to modulate social motivation (Borland et al., 2017) and learning (Hung et al., 2017). It was hypothesized that oxytocin acting in the mesolimbic dopamine system facilitates social salience in aversive social contexts (Shamay-Tsoory & Abu-Akel, 2016). However, recent evidence suggests that OTR in the extended amygdala may play an important role during stressful social contexts. Social defeat stress activates a population of oxytocin neurons in the medioventral bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BNSTmv) in *Peromyscus californicus* (California mice) (Steinman et al., 2016) and C57Bl/6 J mice (Nasanbuyan et al., 2018). The BNST modulates anxiety-related and social behaviors (Lebow & Chen, 2016) and several subregions have strong molecular (Gegenhuber et al., 2022) and anatomical (Campi et al., 2013; Allen & Gorski, 1990) sex differences. Antisense knockdown of oxytocin in the BNST prevented defeat stress-induced social avoidance and social vigilance in female California mice (Duque-Wilckens et al., 2020). These BNST oxytocin neurons project to the anteromedial BNST (BNSTam) where activation of OTR promotes avoidance and vigilance (Duque-Wilckens et al., 2018; Luo et al., 2022). Oxytocin can also promote aversive responses in non-social contexts, as oxytocin in the dorsolateral BNST (BNSTdl) enhanced fear-potentiated startle (FPS) response in rats (Moaddab & Dabrowska, 2017). Together these data suggested that distinct neural circuits mediate the effects of oxytocin in appetitive and aversive social contexts (Steinman et al., 2019a).

129 Most of the studies reviewed above relied on pharmacological manipulations to target OTR function.
130 Pharmacological approaches target both locally expressed post-synaptic receptors and pre-synaptic receptors.
131 Importantly, at least some behavioral effects of OTR can be mediated by pre-synaptic receptors. Dölen and
132 colleagues showed that the behavioral effects of OTR antagonists infused into the NAc were mediated by OTR
133 expressed on presynaptic terminals originating from the dorsal raphe nucleus (Dölen et al., 2013; Nardou et
134 al., 2023). These studies were performed in C57Bl/6 J mice and utilized transgenic mouse lines to specifically
135 target different populations of OTR. The CRISPR/Cas9 gene-editing systems provides a mechanism to
136 perform similar manipulations in species for which transgenic lines are not available. A viral-mediated
137 CRISPR/Cas9-based tool was developed to target OTR expression across a variety of rodent species used as
138 models to study social behavior (Boender et al., 2023). When a guide RNA targeting the *Oxtr* gene was
139 expressed with Cas9, OTR binding was reduced across six different rodent species, including California mice.
140 We used this gene editing system to determine whether locally expressed OTR in the BNST or NAc modulate
141 social approach and social vigilance in female California mice. This viral construct was recently used in a male
142 spiny mouse model in the NAc, which reduced huddling behaviors with strangers as well as some feeding
143 behaviors identifying a role for OTRs in non-reproductive contexts (Fricker et al., 2025).

144 California mice are monogamous rodents in which paired males and females defend joint territories. The
145 high levels of aggression in female California mice make this species ideal for studying the effects of social
146 defeat stress (SDS) in both males and females without the use of CD1 aggressive male mice generally used in
147 C57Bl/6J models (Steinman & Trainor, 2017; Lake & Trainor, 2024). In this study we assessed the impact of
148 OTR knockdown on behavior before and after stress using two behavioral assays in female California mice.
149 Focal mice were tested in a large arena with an unfamiliar female stress-naïve target mouse confined to a
150 small wire cage, which allows for precise measurements of social approach and social vigilance. Social
151 vigilance is a risk assessment behavior in which an individual avoids but attends to a social context (Walker et
152 al., 2023; Wright et al., 2020). Social approach is assessed by time spent within one body length of the cage.
153 Focal mice were also tested in a smaller arena with freely moving stress-naïve and aggressive SDS target
154 mice. This test is ideal for the observation of affiliative and defensive behaviors. Previous studies showed that
155 social approach and social vigilance are modulated by OTR acting within complementary networks that include
156 the BNST and NAc (Duque-Wilckens et al., 2018 and 2020; Luo et al., 2022; Williams et al., 2020). We used a
157 viral strategy to preform CRISPR-Cas9 editing of the oxytocin receptor target gene. We refer to reductions of
158 OTR binding in CRISPR treated groups as “knockdown” within a specific brain region and examined whether
159 changes in locally expressed OTR corresponded to changes in social behavior before and after social defeat
160 stress. We used two behavioral assays to assess the roles of OTR on social approach as well as ethological
161 measures of social interaction.

163 **2 Materials and methods**

165 **2.1 Animals**

166 All studies were conducted using California mice at the University of California, Davis (UCD). Protocols were
167 approved by the UCD Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC). Adult (90 days old) female
168 California mice were studied. Mice were housed with same-sex cagemates after weaning in groups of 2 to 4
169 within clear polypropylene cages. Cages were set up with Sani-Chip bedding (Harlan Laboratories,
170 Indianapolis, IN, USA) and 2 nestlets per cage (Ancare, Bellmore, NY, USA). Mice were kept on a 16L:8D light
171 cycle and had *ad libitum* access to food and water. Viral infusion/surgery were conducted in light cycle, while
172 behavioral testing and stress exposure were performed during the dark cycle.

173 174 **2.2 Intracranial surgeries**

175 Anesthesia was induced via exposure to a 5 % isoflurane mixture with oxygen and then maintained at 2-3.5 %.
176 With a stereotaxic apparatus, mice were bilaterally injected with 300 nL of either the *Oxtr* guide RNA virus or a
177 scramble sequence virus. Mice were randomly assigned to treatment group (CTRL/KD). Coordinates were
178 calculated using the online California mouse brain atlas at brainmaps.org. For NAc we used, AP: +0.51, ML:
179 ± 1.5 , DV: -6.0. For BNST we used, AP: + 0.29, ML: ± 1.1 , DV: -5.85. Mice assigned to OTR knockdown
180 received a viral cocktail consisting of an AAV9 vector expressing *Streptococcus pyogenes* Cas9 under the
181 RSV promoter (Fig. 1A, AAV9-RSV-spCas9, stock titer 1.5×10^{10} genomic copies/ul; injected titer 7.5×10^9
182 gc/ul) and a second AAV9 vector encoding a guide RNA targeting *Oxtr* (AAV9-U6-gRNA(Δ OXTR.1)-CMV-
183 eGFP, 5'-GGTGCTTCATGAAAAAGAAG-3', stock titer 2.0×10^{10} gc/ul stock; injected titer 1.0×10^{10} gc/ul)
184 mixed in a 1:1 (Boender et al., 2023). This guide RNA targets a sequence of the *Oxtr* gene that is evolutionarily
185 conserved across several rodent species. Control mice received a cocktail consisting of the Cas9 vector and a
186 scrambled gRNA sequence. All mice were given a carprofen injection at the beginning of surgery (1.45 mg/kg
187 dosage) and then 3 daily doses during recovery. Skin staples were used to close the skin and were removed 7
188 days post-surgery. Surgical controls were not included in the present study. Pre-stress behaviors across all
189 experimental groups were comparable to what we have reported in California mice that did not undergo AAV
190 manipulation (Trainor et al., 2011; Steinman et al., 2016).

191 192 **2.3 Behavioral timeline**

193 Three weeks after surgery, all mice were tested in a Large Arena Social Interaction test (Fig. 1B). In prairie
194 voles 2 weeks of viral expression were sufficient to decrease OTR binding (Boender et al. 2023), so we are
195 confident that mice assigned to knockdown had reduced OTR expression when these behavior tests were
196 conducted. One day later mice were tested in a Small Arena Social Interaction test. In this test target mice are
197 not caged, allowing direct contact with focal mice. Following these behavioral tests all focal mice underwent
198 three consecutive days of social defeat. One week later both the large and small arena social interaction tests
199 were repeated as described above. Mice were never tested with the same Target or aggressive Target mouse
200 (except for post-stress interaction with aggressive Target in the small arena) in the large or small arena tests.

201 202 **2.4 Large arena test**

This test consisted of 3 phases: Open Field, Acclimation, and Interaction (Greenberg et al. 2014). Focal mice were placed in the large rectangular arena, made of opaque white acrylic (89 X 63 X 60 cm). Each phase lasted 3 min and was recorded via AnyMaze software. In the Open Field phase, mice were allowed to explore the empty arena. Time spent in the center of the arena and total distance traveled was recorded. This was followed by the Acclimation phase where an empty wire cage (14 X 17 X 14.5 cm) was placed on one end of the arena. Finally, in the last phase an unfamiliar stress-naïve female target mouse was placed inside the wire cage. This test was repeated 1 week after social defeat stress. A different target mouse was used from the pre-stress test to post-stress testing.

2.5 Small Arena test

The small arena test was conducted in an acrylic chamber (51 X 25.4 X 76 cm) connected to a small chamber with a sliding door for introducing target mice. In the Open Field phase, focal mice entered through the attached chamber (13 X 10 X 18 cm) and explored the empty arena for 3 min. We then assessed interactions with target mice using target mice with (aggressive) or without (naïve) prior experience winning aggressive encounters (Wright et al., 2023; Luo et al., 2024). First a female naïve target mouse was introduced to the arena and interactions with the focal mouse were recorded for 3 min. The target mouse was removed and then an aggressive female target mouse was introduced to the arena for a final 3 min. This test was repeated 1 week after social defeat stress (Fig. 1B). In the post-stress tests, different target mice were used from the pre-stress tests. However, each focal mouse had interacted with the aggressive target mouse from social defeat encounters. All videos were scored using BORIS by a single trained observer without knowledge of the treatment group status of the focal mouse. Here affiliative (nose-to-nose sniffing, anogenital sniffing, and bodily sniffing), coping (auto-grooming and flipping), defensive (lunging), and monitoring behaviors (social vigilance) were recorded. We define social vigilance as a mouse orienting their head to a conspecific while simultaneously avoiding it. Social approach was not assessed in this test due to the size of the arena and the lack of machine learning to score “passing” behavior versus “approach.” Flipping behavior is a motivated behavior in California mouse that has been identified as a coping behavior (Minie et al., 2021).

2.6 Social defeat stress

After testing in the large and small arena tests, all focal mice underwent social defeat stress with aggressive resident females. Each mouse experienced 3 consecutive days of social defeat stress as previously described (Greenberg et al., 2014). On each day, the focal mouse was placed into the home cage of a sexually experienced aggressive resident same-sex mouse. Resident aggressive females were paired with a vasectomized male as this results in more consistent territorial aggression, but were removed during the same-sex defeat (Trainor et al. 2013). Each episode of this defeat lasts 7 min or until the intruder/experimental mouse is attacked/defeated a total of 7 times, whichever comes first. After testing, experimental mice are immediately placed back in their homecage. Post-stress testing of focal mice was conducted one week after the last episode of defeat. This 3-day protocol does not induce physical injury to focal or resident mice and

240 results in behavioral changes that can be observed up to 10 weeks after the last episode of defeat (Steinman
241 et al., 2016; Trainor et al., 2011).

243 **2.7 Histology and autoradiography**

244 After post-stress behavior testing mice were anesthetized with isoflurane, decapitated, and brains were
245 removed to be flash frozen on dry ice. Brains were stored at -80 °C and then cut with a cryostat at 20 µm and
246 mounted directly on frost plus slides in series. One set of slides was used to determine viral spread by
247 assessing green fluorescent protein (GFP) expression (Fig 1C). These images were used to determine spread
248 of the virus. Adjacent sections were saved on an alternate of slides for OTR autoradiography (as in Hartman et
249 al., 2018). Briefly, slides were removed from -80 °C storage, thawed at room temperature for 1 h, fixed in a
250 light 0.1 % paraformaldehyde (pH 7.4) solution, and washed twice in Tris Buffer, before being incubated in the
251 tracer buffer at room temperature for 60 min. Tracer buffer consisted of 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer (7.4 pH) with 10
252 mM MgCl₂, 0.1 % bovine serum albumin, and 50 pM of radiotracer. For OTR binding, [¹²⁵I]-ornithine vasotocin
253 analog [¹²⁵I-OVTA] [vasotocin, d(CH₂)₅[Tyr(Me)₂, Thr₄, Orn₈, (125I)Tyr₉-NH₂]; 2200 Ci/mmol] was used
254 (Revvity, Waltham, MA, USA). Previously we observed that the CRISPR tools we used in this study reduced
255 OTR binding but not V1aR binding in California mice (Boender et al., 2023). Following the incubation period,
256 unbound radioligand was removed by 4 washes in 50 mM Tris buffer and 2 % MgCl₂, pH 7.4, and then dipped
257 in dH₂O and air dried.

258 The slides were dried overnight and exposed to Cytiva Amersha, Hyperfilm (Cytiva Life Sciences,
259 Washington, DC, USA) for 4 days with a set of ¹²⁵I standard microscales (American Radiolabeled Chemicals,
260 St. Louis, MO, USA). We then used MCID Core Digital Densitometry system (Cambridge, UK) to quantify *Oxtr*
261 binding in each target brain. For each specimen, optical binding density (OBD) values were calculated for each
262 region of interest (ROI), as well as one background area where no binding was detected. Three separate
263 measurements for each ROI were taken per specimen and averaged. For each specimen, the average
264 background binding value was subtracted from each average ROI measurement to yield normalized OBDs
265 across specimens. There were 2 samples that were damaged in the slide processing and treatment
266 designation for knockdown was determined with GFP photomicrographs of coronal sections of NAc and BNST.
267 Based on oxytocin receptor binding and GFP spread, two mice were reassigned treatment groups (one NAc to
268 BNST, one BNST to NAc) and four mice had OTR binding levels in the BNST and NAc that were below the
269 lowest value observed in control groups. Based on these observations these mice were reassigned to a NAc +
270 BNST knockdown group. We limit our inferences from this group due to the small sample size.

272 **2.8 Statistical analysis**

273 Autoradiography data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA in R with planned comparisons to compare
274 treatment groups with controls. For large arena tests behavior was analyzed with one-way ANOVA followed by
275 planned comparisons. We used paired t-test within each treatment group to test if there were differences
276 before versus after stress. For the small arena tests each behavior, we conducted separate analyses by social
277 partner type (naive vs. aggressive target) and timepoint (pre-stress vs. post-stress). For small arena tests each

278 dependent variable was tested across treatment groups using nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis test with pairwise
279 comparisons using the Mann-Whitney U test.

282 **3 RESULTS**

284 **3.1 OTR Knockdown in the BNSTam and NAc in female California mice**

285 Autoradiography analysis (Fig. 2A) showed that *Oxtr* CRISPR/Cas9-mediated knockdown altered OTR binding
286 in the BNSTam (Fig. 2B, $F_{3,26} = 13.69$, $p < 0.001$) and NAc (Fig. 2C, $F_{3,26} = 12.18$, $p < 0.001$). Mice assigned to
287 BNST knockdown had reduced OTR binding in BNST (Fig. 2B, planned comparison, $p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d =$
288 2.36) but not NAc (Fig. 2C) compared to controls. In contrast, mice assigned to NAc knockdown had reduced
289 binding in NAc (Fig. 2C, planned comparison $p < 0.001$, $d = 0.48$) but not BNST (Fig. 2B) compared to
290 controls. In some animals binding was reduced in both the BNST and NAc, so these animals were included as
291 a separate group as "BNST + NAc KD." There were no differences in OTR binding in the LS (Fig. 2D),
292 suggesting that our manipulations were site-specific.

294 **3.2 OTR Knockdown within the BNSTam prevents stress-induced changes in social approach and 295 vigilance in the large arena**

296 Three weeks after bilateral CRISPR/Cas9 injections, adult female California mice were tested in the large
297 arena test to measure baseline behaviors before and after social defeat stress (Fig. 3A). In pre-stress
298 observations there were no differences in social approach (Fig. 3B) or vigilance (Fig. 3C). After stress, OTR
299 knockdown showed a trend to affect social approach behavior ($F_{3,27} = 2.50$, $p = 0.07$). Planned comparisons
300 showed that BNST ($p = 0.04$, $d = 0.43$) and BNST+NAc ($p = 0.04$, $d = 0.01$) knockdown groups had higher
301 social approach compared to controls (Fig. 3B). For social vigilance there were significant differences between
302 groups after stress (Fig. 3C, $F_{3,27} = 3.50$, $p = 0.03$). Planned comparisons showed lower vigilance in the NAc
303 group ($p = 0.01$, $d = 0.26$) and a trend for lower vigilance in the BNST+NAc knockdown ($p = 0.052$, $d = 0.30$)
304 compared to controls. Decreased vigilance in the BNST knockdown group compared to control was also at
305 trend level ($p = 0.06$, $d = 0.44$). In paired comparisons, controls before and after stress increased their
306 vigilance ($p = 0.001$, $d = -1.19$) and decreased their approach ($p = 0.008$, $d = 0.82$). Effects of stress were not
307 significant in the other treatment groups. To determine whether the extent of OTR knockdown affected
308 behavior after stress, we examined correlations between receptor density and social approach in the BNST
309 knockdown group and controls (Fig. 4). Receptor density was not significantly correlated with social approach
310 (Fig. 4A, Control: $R = -0.16$, $p = 0.56$; BNST knockdown: $R = -0.17$, $p = 0.71$) or vigilance (Fig. 4B, Control $R =$
311 -0.001 , $p = 0.98$; BNST knockdown $R = 0.121$, $p = 0.8$). In contrast, a strong negative correlation between
312 social approach and vigilance was observed after stress in controls ($R = -0.640$, $p = 0.007$), whereas the same
313 relationship in BNST knockdown mice showed a similar relationship that did not reach significance ($R = -0.682$,
314 $p = 0.09$).

315 There were no differences in time spent in the center of the arena or total distance in the open field phase
316 (Fig. 5 B and C). During the acclimation phase, when the target mouse was absent, there were no differences
317 in approach to the empty cage before stress (Fig. 5D). After stress, approach to the empty cage in control mice
318 did not differ from before stress levels, suggesting that mice did not habituate to the cage. There were effects
319 of knockdown after stress ($F_{3,27} = 3.920$, $p = 0.02$). Mice with BNST knockdown showed higher levels of
320 approach to the empty cage compared to controls ($p = 0.01$, $d = -0.42$), whereas NAc knockdown and
321 BNST+NAc knockdown mice did not differ from controls.

323 **3.3 OTR Knockdown does not blunt effects of stress in the small arena**

324 Across all behaviors we quantified, there were no effects of OTR knockdown after stress compared to controls.
325 The only effects of OTR knockdown were observed pre-stress in affiliative nose-to-nose sniffing with naïve
326 target mice (Fig. 6H, Kruskal-Wallis $H = 17.84$, $p = 0.0005$), with reduced sniffing in BNST ($p = 0.0007$, $d =$
327 1.48) and BNST+NAc knockdown ($p = 0.007$, $d = 1.21$) compared to controls before stress. There were no
328 effects of OTR knockdown on more assertive anogenital sniffing data before stress. However, anogenital
329 sniffing was significantly reduced post-stress in controls with the naïve target mice (Fig. 6D, $p = 0.0002$, $d =$
330 1.14) but not in other groups. A similar effect of stress on anogenital sniffing was observed post-stress with
331 aggressive target mice (Fig 6I, $p = 0.02$, $d = 0.70$). There were also no treatment effects on vigilance before or
332 after stress (Fig. 6 E and J, Target: $H = 1.92$, $p = 0.59$; Aggressive Target: $H = 3.07$, $p = 0.38$). After stress in
333 paired comparisons, vigilance directed towards naïve target mice was increased in control ($p = 0.007$, $d = 1.07$)
334 and BNST knockdown ($p = 0.0156$, $d = 1.51$) mice compared to pre-stress observations (Fig. 6E). Similar
335 results were observed with vigilance directed towards aggressive target mice, as stress increased vigilance in
336 control mice ($p = 0.005$, $d = 1.33$) but not in the BNST knockdown group ($p = 0.09$). No differences were
337 observed in lunging behaviors (Fig. 6F and K). There were no effects of OTR knockdown on flipping behavior
338 (Fig. 6G and L) although reduced flipping was observed post-stress in control animals interacting with naïve
339 target mice (Fig. 6G, $p = 0.032$, $d = 0.59$).

341 **4 Discussion**

342
343 Using CRISPR/Cas9 we observed that experimentally reduced OTR expression in the BNST of female
344 California mice blocked stress-induced decreases in social approach. Additionally, BNST knockdown of OTRs
345 increased approach to a novel object after stress. Unexpectedly, effects of BNST OTR knockdown had more
346 modest effects on social vigilance in the large arena and small arena. These observations contrast with
347 pharmacological studies where BNST OTR antagonists increased social approach and decreased social
348 vigilance in stressed female California mice (Duque-Wilckens et al., 2018) and infusions of OTR agonists
349 decreased approach and increased vigilance in unstressed males and females (Duque-Wilckens et al. 2020;
350 Luo et al., 2022). While the sample size was low, knockdown of OTR in NAc significantly reduced stress-
351 induced social vigilance without affecting social approach in the large arena. Previous pharmacological studies
352 reported that activation of OTR in NAc in stressed females increased social approach and decreased vigilance

(Williams et al., 2020). A key difference from our previous pharmacology studies is that here OTR manipulations were performed before stress exposure. This raises the possibility that activation of OTR during stress exposure contributes to behavioral changes in female California mice. Overall, our findings suggest that local BNST OTRs modulate stress-induced decreases in social approach.

4.1 Effects of oxytocin receptor on social approach

Our analyses of viral spread and autoradiography indicate that mice assigned to the BNST knockdown had reduced OTR expression selectively in the BNST. This suggests that behavioral effects in this group are mediated by locally expressed receptor on post-synaptic neurons or glia. This finding aligns with prior pharmacological studies where social approach is reduced in stress naïve female California mice when oxytocin receptor agonists are infused into the BNST (Duque-Wilckens et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2022), and activation of OTR in the BNST after stress decreases approach (Duque-Wilckens et al., 2018). Notably, BNST OTR knockdown also increased approach to an empty cage after stress, suggesting that OTR in BNST can modulate exploratory behavior in non-social contexts. In California mice, social defeat generally does not affect approach to the empty cage in the acclimation phase (Trainor et al. 2011 and 2013; Greenberg et al. 2014; Duque-Wilckens et al. 2018). However, males and females treated with an infusion of 1 ng of oxytocin into the BNST showed avoidance of the empty cage (Duque-Wilckens & Trainor unpublished data). It is possible that defeat may not influence approach to an empty cage because oxytocin is not released in this context. In the small arena the effects of OTR knockdown in BNST were more limited when focal mice could freely interact with target mice. Knockdown of OTR in the BNST reduced nose-to-nose sniffing of aggressive target mice before stress, but not after stress. Thus, OTR in BNST may play a more important role in modulating social interactions when individuals are not in close contact. It's possible that arginine vasopressin (AVP) may play a stronger role in modulating behavior when individuals are in close contact. Vasopressin can activate V1a receptors and previous studies reporting effects of V1 receptor regulation of behavior involve animals physically interacting with one another such as pair bonding (Winslow et al., 1993), social communication (Febo & Ferris, 2016; Freeman et al., 2018) and aggression (Duque-Wilckens et al. 2016, Taylor et al., 2022; Terranova et al., 2016).

In the NAc, previous studies in California mice indicated the importance of OTR in regulating social approach. Social defeat stress decreases OTR binding (Duque-Wilckens et al., 2018) and *Oxtr* mRNA (Williams et al., 2020) in the NAc of male and female California mice while OTR antagonists infused into the NAc reduced social approach (Williams et al., 2020). Here knockdown of OTR in the NAc did not reduce social approach before or after stress. Although this comparison is under-powered relative to the BNST group, this observation is consistent with previous studies in male mice documenting a role for presynaptic OTR in the NAc (Dolen et al. 2013; Nardou et al. 2019). Dopaminergic inputs from the ventral tegmental area (VTA) regulate social approach in C57BL/6 J mice by encoding reward value and reinforcing social interactions. Optogenetic activation of VTA dopamine neurons enhances social preference, while inhibition reduces it (Paquelet et al., 2022). Similarly, serotonergic inputs from the dorsal raphe nucleus (DRN) contribute to

learning-related behaviors, with DRN à VTA 5H-T neurons preferentially encoding reward-related cues and dynamically regulating social approach based on prior experience. In juvenile C57BL/6J mice, Dolen and colleagues showed that the behavioral effects of OTR antagonists infused into the NAc were mediated by OTR expressed on presynaptic terminals originating from the DRN that directly affect conditioned place preference learning (Dolen et al., 2013). These findings suggest that social approach behaviors in the NAc may be shaped by coordinated inputs from DRN à VTA serotonin neurons and/or VTA dopamine neurons.

4.2 Effects of oxytocin receptor on social vigilance

Effects of OTR knockdown on social vigilance were distinct from effects on social approach. In the large arena, BNST OTR knockdown produced a non-significant trend for reduced vigilance after stress compared to controls. In previous pharmacology studies (which target pre- and post-synaptic receptors), activation of BNST OTR increased social vigilance in both male and female California mice (Duque- Wilckens et al., 2018 and 2020; Luo et al., 2022). Since post-stress social approach was affected by BNST OTR knockdown, we assessed the relationship between social approach and vigilance. If pre-synaptic OTR in the BNST were controlling social vigilance, we would expect that the negative relationship between social approach and vigilance would be eliminated by OTR knockdown (which should not impact pre-synaptic receptors). Approach and vigilance were inversely related in both control and BNST knockdown mice, which does not provide strong evidence for a role of presynaptic OTR in controlling vigilance. We also examined whether the extent of knockdown was correlated with vigilance and observed little evidence that mice with higher vigilance in the BNST knockdown group had more receptor density (e.g. less effective knockdown). One possibility is that activation of OTR in BNST during episodes of social defeat may help encode the salience of an aversive interaction. Our knockdown approach reduced receptor expression before episodes of social defeat whereas our previous antagonist experiment only inactivated OTR after defeat (Duque-Wilckens et al., 2018). Encoding effects of OTR during episodes of social stress may be stronger in the NAc.

Knockdown of OTR in the NAc significantly reduced vigilance after stress in the large arena, even though there was less statistical power due to smaller sample size than the BNST group. Similar patterns were observed in the small arena. Suppressed vigilance in the NAc knockdown group was an unexpected finding but could reflect a learning component. In the NAc, interactions between oxytocin and dopamine are known to modulate social behaviors (Liu & Wang, 2003). There is strong evidence that dopamine signaling in the NAc organizes responses to aversive experiences, with D2 receptor-expressing medium spiny neurons in the core supporting the encoding and recall of aversive foot-shocks (Belilos et al., 2023). In Syrian hamsters, dopamine release in the NAc core increases during both winning and losing aggressive encounters (Cross et al., 2025), and pharmacological blockade of dopamine receptors in the NAc during losing blocks increases in submissive behavior in future social encounters (Gray et al., 2015). This suggests that effects of OTR knockdown in NAc on vigilance behavior, similar to dopamine receptor signaling, may depend on its timing relative to social defeat. Overall, these findings raise the possibility that the NAc is a site where oxytocin and dopamine interact during stress to influence vigilance behaviors.

5 Conclusions

These results demonstrate that locally expressed OTRs in the BNST and NAc make distinct contributions to stress-induced social behaviors. In the BNST, OTR knockdown decreased social avoidance and increased exploratory behaviors after stress, while effects on vigilance were modest. Our results show that knockdown in the NAc was sufficient in modulating social vigilance behavior after stress, consistent with previous work that shows social stress increases dopamine release in the NAc (Tidey & Miczek, 1996). Effects of OTR knockdown in the NAc on vigilance suggest a possible role for oxytocin in the mesolimbic dopamine system for encoding socially aversive experiences. Together, these findings add to evidence from pharmacology studies that suggest that BNST and NAc OTRs have distinct effects on social approach and vigilance. Future studies could explore how OTR modulates social avoidance and vigilance in male California mice, which can be observed after acute social defeat (Butler-Struben et al., 2025). Further work is needed to determine how these populations of OTR act during episodes of stress versus modulating the long-lasting effects of stress on behavior.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Valentina Cea Salazar: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Arjen J. Boender:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Adele M.H. Seelke:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Liam Gaard:** Formal analysis. **Sabrina L. Mederos:** Investigation. **Sophia Rogers:** Investigation. **Xiomara Z. Gutierrez:** Investigation. **Karen L. Bales:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Larry J. Young:** Resources. **Brian C. Trainor:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank H. Butler-Struben, PhD and P. Luo, PhD for their help in surgical training and optimizing the micro-injection protocol for this study. Illustrations for figures were done with biorender.com. This work was supported by an Ikerbasque Research Fellowship to AJB, P50MH100023 and R01MH112788 to LJY, OD P51OD011132 to EPC (Primate center base grant), and NIMH R01MH121829 and R01MH121829-04S1 to BCT.

References

Abramowitz, J.S., Deacon, B., 2010. Anxiety and its disorders: implications for pharmacotherapy. *Clin. Psychol. Sci. Pract.* 17, 104–106. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2850.2010.01199.x>.

- 464 Allen, L.S., & Gorski, R.A., 1990. Sex difference in the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis of the human brain. *J.*
465 *Comp. Neurol.* 302(4), 697–706. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cne.903020402>.
- 466 Bartz, J.A., Zaki, J., Bolger, N., & Ochsner, K.N., 2011. Social effects of oxytocin in humans: context and
467 person matter. *Trends Cogn. Sci.* 15(7), 301–309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2011.05.002>.
- 468 Belilos, A., Gray, C., Sanders, C., Black, D., Mays, E., Richie, C., Sengupta, A., Hake, H., & Francis, T.C.
469 (2023). Nucleus accumbens local circuit for cue-dependent aversive learning. *Cell Rep.* 42(12),
470 113488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2023.113488>.
- 471 Boender, A.J., Boon, M., Albers, H.E., Eck, S.R., Fricker, B.A., Kelly, A.M., LeDoux, J.E., Motta, S.C.,
472 Shrestha, P., Taylor, J.H., Trainor, B.C., Triana-Del Rio, R., & Young, L.J., 2023. An
473 AAV-CRISPR/Cas9 strategy for gene editing across divergent rodent species: targeting neural oxytocin
474 receptors as a proof of concept. *Sci. Adv.* 9(22), eadf4950. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adf4950>.
- 475 Borland, J.M., Frantz, K.J., Aiani, L.M., Grantham, K.N., Song, Z., & Albers, H.E., 2017. A novel operant task to
476 assess social reward and motivation in rodents. *J. Neurosci. Methods.* 287, 80–88.
477 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2017.06.003>.
- 478 Butler-Struben, H.M., Black, A.M., Wright, S.M., Dye, A.F., & Trainor, B.C., 2025. Acute and vicarious effects of
479 social defeat stress on social behavior in California mice (*Peromyscus californicus*). *Anim. Behav.*
480 222, 123098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2025.123098>.
- 481 Campi, K.L., Jameson, C.E., & Trainor, B.C. (2013). Sexual dimorphism in the brain of the monogamous
482 California mouse (*Peromyscus californicus*). *Brain Behav. Evol.* 81(4), 236–249.
483 <https://doi.org/10.1159/000353260>.
- 484 Cross, E.A., Borland, J.M., Shaughnessy, E.K., Lee, S.D., Vu, V., Sambor, E.A., Meisel, R.L., Huhman, K.L., &
485 Albers, H.E., 2025. Distinct subcircuits within the mesolimbic dopamine system encode the salience
486 and valence of social stimuli. *Psychopharmacology Advance online publication* doi:10.1007/s00213-
487 025-06793-z.
- 488 Dölen, G., Darvishzadeh, A., Huang, K.W., Malenka, R.C., 2013. Social reward requires coordinated activity of
489 nucleus accumbens oxytocin and serotonin. *Nature.* 501, 179–184.
490 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature12518>.
- 491 Duque-Wilckens, N., Steinman, M.Q., Busnelli, M., Chini, B., Yokoyama, S., Pham, M., Laredo, S.A., Hao, R.,
492 Perkeybile, A.M., Minie, V.A., Tan, P.B., Bales, K.L., Trainor, B.C., 2018. Oxytocin receptors in the
493 anteromedial bed nucleus of the stria terminalis promote stress-induced social avoidance in female
494 California mice. *Biol. Psychiatry.* 83, 203–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2017.08.024>.
- 495 Duque-Wilckens, N., Torres, L.Y., Yokoyama, S., Minie, V.A., Tran, A.M., Petkova, S.P., Hao, R., Ramos-
496 Maciel, S., Rios, R.A., Jackson, K., Flores-Ramirez, F.J., Garcia-Carachure, I., Pesavento, P.A.,
497 Iñiguez, S.D., Grinevich, V., & Trainor, B.C., 2020. Extrahypothalamic oxytocin neurons drive stress-
498 induced social vigilance and avoidance. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 117(42), 26406–26413.
499 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2011890117>.
- 500 Febo, M., & Ferris, C.F., 2014. Oxytocin and vasopressin modulation of the neural correlates of motivation and
501 emotion: results from functional MRI studies in awake rats. *Brain Res.* 1580, 8–21.
502 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres.2014.01.019>.
- 503 Freeman, A.R., Hare, J.F., Anderson, W.G., & Caldwell, H.K., 2018. Effects of arginine vasopressin on
504 Richardson's ground squirrel social and vocal behavior. *Behav. Neurosci.* 132(1), 34–50.
505 <https://doi.org/10.1037/bne0000225>.
- 506 Fricker, B.A., Boender, A.J., Young, L.J., & Kelly, A.M., 2025. Not just for bonding: nucleus accumbens
507 oxytocin receptors facilitate huddling with strangers and feeding in male spiny mice.
508 *Psychoneuroendocrinology.* 178, 107496. Advance online publication.
509 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psyneuen.2025.107496>.
- 510 Gegenhuber, B., Wu, M.V., Bronstein, R., & Tollkuhn, J., 2022. Gene regulation by gonadal hormone receptors
511 underlies brain sex differences. *Nature.* 606(7912), 153–159. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04686-1>.
- 512 Gimpl, G., & Fahrenholz, F., 2001. The oxytocin receptor system: structure, function, and regulation. *Physiol.*
513 *Rev.* 81(2), 629–683. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.2001.81.2.629>.
- 514 Giovanna, G., Damiani, S., Fusar-Poli, L., Rocchetti, M., Brondino, N., de Cagna, F., Mori, A., & Politi, P.,
515 2020. Intranasal oxytocin as a potential therapeutic strategy in post-traumatic stress disorder: A
516 systematic review. *Psychoneuroendocrinology.* 115, 104605.
517 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psyneuen.2020.104605>.
- 518

- 519 Gray, C.L., Norvelle, A., Larkin, T., & Huhman, K.L., 2015. Dopamine in the nucleus accumbens modulates the
520 memory of social defeat in Syrian hamsters (*Mesocricetus auratus*). *Behav. Brain Res.* 286, 22–28.
521 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbr.2015.02.030>.
- 522 Greenberg, G.D., Laman-Maharg, A., Campi, K.L., Voigt, H., Orr, V.N., Schaal, L., Trainor, B.C., 2014. Sex
523 differences in stress-induced social withdrawal: role of brain derived neurotrophic factor in the bed
524 nucleus of the stria terminalis. *Front. Behav. Neurosci.* 7, 223.
525 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2013.00223>.
- 526 Gutkowska, J., & Jankowski, M., 2012. Oxytocin revisited: its role in cardiovascular regulation. *J.*
527 *Neuroendocrinol.* 24(4), 599–608. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2826.2011.02235.x>.
- 528 Hartman, S., Freeman, S.M., Bales, K.L., & Belsky, J., 2018. Prenatal stress as a risk-and an opportunity-
529 Factor. *Psychol. Sci.* 29(4), 572–580. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797617739983>.
- 530 Hung, L.W., Neuner, S., Polepalli, J.S., Beier, K.T., Wright, M., Walsh, J.J., Lewis, E.M., Luo, L., Deisseroth,
531 K., Dölen, G., & Malenka, R.C., 2017. Gating of social reward by oxytocin in the ventral tegmental area.
532 *Science (New York, N.Y.)*. 357 (6358), 1406–1411. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aan4994>.
- 533 Kessler, R.C., Petukhova, M., Sampson, N.A., Zaslavsky, A.M., & Wittchen, H.-U., 2012. Twelve-month and
534 lifetime prevalence and lifetime morbid risk of anxiety and mood disorders in the United States. *Int. J.*
535 *Methods Psychiatr. Res.* 21(3), 169–184. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mpr.1359>.
- 536 Lake, A.A., & Trainor, B.C., 2024. Leveraging the unique social organization of California mice to study circuit-
537 specific effects of oxytocin on behavior. *Horm. Behav.* 160, 105487.
538 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2024.105487>.
- 539 Lebow, M.A., & Chen, A., 2016. Overshadowed by the amygdala: the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis
540 emerges as key to psychiatric disorders. *Mol. Psychiatry.* 21(4), 450–463.
541 <https://doi.org/10.1038/mp.2016.1>.
- 542 Liu, Y., & Wang, Z. X., 2003. Nucleus accumbens oxytocin and dopamine interact to regulate pair bond
543 formation in female prairie voles. *Neuroscience.* 121(3), 537–544. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0306-4522\(03\)00555-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0306-4522(03)00555-4).
- 544 Luo, P.X., Zakharenkov, H.C., Torres, L.Y., Rios, R.A., Gegenhuber, B., Black, A.M., Xu, C.K., Minie, V.A.,
545 Tran, A.M., Tollkuhn, J., Trainor, B.C., 2022. Oxytocin receptor behavioral effects and cell types in the
546 bed nucleus of the stria terminalis. *Horm. Behav.* 143, 105203.
547 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2022.105203>.
- 548 Luo, P. X., Serna Godoy, A., Zakharenkov, H.C., Vang, N., Wright, E.C., Balantac, T.A., Archdeacon, S.C.,
549 Black, A.M., Lake, A.A., Ramirez, A.V., Lozier, L.E., Perez, M.D., Bhargal, I., Desta, N.M., & Trainor,
550 B.C., 2024. Hypocretin in the nucleus accumbens shell modulates social approach in female but not
551 male California mice. *Neuropsychopharmacology.* 49(13), 2000–2010. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-024-01937-9>.
- 552 Macdonald, K., & Feifel, D., 2013. Helping oxytocin deliver: considerations in the development of oxytocin-
553 based therapeutics for brain disorders. *Front. Neurosci.* 7, 35. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2013.00035>
- 554 MacDonald, K., & Feifel, D., 2014. Oxytocin's role in anxiety: a critical appraisal. *Brain Res.* 1580, 22–56.
555 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres.2014.01.025>.
- 556 Minie, V.A., Petric, R., Ramos-Maciél, S., Wright, E.C., Trainor, B.C., & Duque-Wilckens, N., 2021. Enriched
557 laboratory housing increases sensitivity to social stress in female California mice (*Peromyscus*
558 *californicus*). *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 241, 105381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2021.105381>.
- 559 Moaddab, M., & Dabrowska, J., 2017. Oxytocin receptor neurotransmission in the dorsolateral bed nucleus of
560 the stria terminalis facilitates the acquisition of cued fear in the fear-potentiated startle paradigm in rats.
561 *Neuropharmacology.* 121, 130–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2017.04.039>.
- 562 Modi, M.E., & Young, L.J., 2012. The oxytocin system in drug discovery for autism: animal models and novel
563 therapeutic strategies. *Horm. Behav.* 61(3), 340–350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2011.12.010>.
- 564 Nardou, R., Lewis, E.M., Rothhaas, R., Xu, R., Yang, A., Boyden, E., & Dölen, G., 2019. Oxytocin-dependent
565 reopening of a social reward learning critical period with MDMA. *Nature.* 569(7754), 116–120.
566 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1075-9>.
- 567 Nardou, R., Sawyer, E., Song, Y.J., Wilkinson, M., Padovan-Hernandez, Y., de Deus, J.L., Wright, N., Lama,
568 C., Faltin, S., Goff, L.A., Stein-O'Brien, G.L., Dölen, G., 2023. Psychedelics reopen the social reward
569 learning critical period. *Nature* 618, 790–798. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06204-3>.
- 570 Nasanbuyan, N., Yoshida, M., Takayanagi, Y., Inutsuka, A., Nishimori, K., Yamanaka, A., & Onaka, T., 2018.
571 Oxytocin-oxytocin receptor systems facilitate social defeat posture in male mice. *Endocrinology.* 159(2),
572 763–775. <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.2017-00606>.
- 573
- 574

- 575 Osakada, T., Yan, R., Jiang, Y., Wei, D., Tabuchi, R., Dai, B., Wang, X., Zhao, G., Wang, C.X., Liu, J.-J., Tsien,
576 R.W., Mar., A.C., Lin, D., 2024. A dedicated hypothalamic oxytocin circuit controls aversive social
577 learning. *Nature*. 626, 347-356.
- 578 Paquelet, G.E., Carrion, K., Lacefield, C.O., Zhou, P., Hen, R., & Miller, B.R., 2022. Single-cell activity and
579 network properties of dorsal raphe nucleus serotonin neurons during emotionally salient behaviors.
580 *Neuron*. 110(16), 2664–2679.e8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2022.05.015>.
- 581 Rashidi, M., Simon, J.J., Bertsch, K., Wegen, G.V., Ditzen, B., Flor, H., Grinevich, V., Wolf, R.C., & Herpertz,
582 S. C., 2025. Effects of intranasal oxytocin on fear extinction learning. *Neuropsychopharmacology*.
583 50(3), 548–555. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-024-01996-y>.
- 584 Rigney, N., Horie, K., Guo, J.-D., Blumenthal, S.A., Johnson, Z.V., Young, L.J., 2025. Neural connectivity of
585 oxytocin receptor-expressing neurons in the nucleus accumbens and their role in social attachment.
586 *Horm. Behav.* 171, 105726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2025.105726>.
- 587 Salgado, S., & Kaplitt, M. G., 2015. The Nucleus accumbens: A comprehensive review. *Stereotact. Funct.*
588 *Neurosurg.* 93(2), 75–93. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000368279>.
- 589 Schultebrasucks, K., Maslahati, T., Wingenfeld, K., Hellmann-Regen, J., Kraft, J., Kownatzki, M., Behnia, B.,
590 Ripke, S., Otte, C., & Roepke, S., 2022. Intranasal oxytocin administration impacts the acquisition and
591 consolidation of trauma-associated memories: a double-blind randomized placebo-controlled
592 experimental study in healthy women. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. (5), 1046–1054.
593 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-021-01247-4>.
- 594 Shamay-Tsoory, S. G., & Abu-Akel, A., 2016. The social salience hypothesis of oxytocin. *Biol. Psychiatry*.
595 79(3), 194–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2015.07.020>.
- 596 Smith, C.J.W., Mogavero, J.N., Tulimieri, M.T., & Veenema, A. H., 2017. Involvement of the oxytocin system in
597 the nucleus accumbens in the regulation of juvenile social novelty-seeking behavior. *Horm. Behav.* 93,
598 94–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2017.05.005>.
- 599 Steinman, M.Q., & Trainor, B.C., 2017. Sex differences in the effects of social defeat on brain and behavior in
600 the California mouse: Insights from a monogamous rodent. *Semin. Cell Dev. Biol.* 61, 92–98.
601 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semcd.2016.06.021>.
- 602 Steinman, M. Q., Duque-Wilckens, N., & Trainor, B. C. (2019). Complementary Neural Circuits for Divergent
603 Effects of Oxytocin: Social Approach Versus Social Anxiety. *Biological psychiatry*, 85(10), 792–801.
604 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2018.10.008>.
- 605 Steinman, M.Q., Duque-Wilckens, N., Greenberg, G.D., Hao, R., Campi, K.L., Laredo, S.A., Laman-Maharg,
606 A., Manning, C.E., Doig, I.E., Lopez, E.M., Walch, K., Bales, K.L., & Trainor, B.C., 2016. Sex-specific
607 effects of stress on oxytocin neurons correspond with responses to intranasal oxytocin. *Biol. Psychiatry*.
608 80(5), 406–414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2015.10.007>.
- 609 Steinman, M.Q., Duque-Wilckens, N., Trainor, B.C., 2019a. Complementary neural circuits for divergent effects
610 of oxytocin: social approach versus social anxiety. *Biol. Psychiatry*. 85, 792–801.
611 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2018.10.008>.
- 612 Tabak, B.A., Rosenfield, D., Sunahara, C.S., Alvi, T., Szeto, A., & Mendez, A.J., 2022. Social anxiety is
613 associated with greater peripheral oxytocin reactivity to psychosocial stress.
614 *Psychoneuroendocrinology*. 140, 105712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psyneuen.2022.105712>.
- 615 Taylor, J.H., Walton, J.C., McCann, K.E., Norvelle, A., Liu, Q., Vander Velden, J. W., Borland, J.M., Hart, M.,
616 Jin, C., Huhman, K.L., Cox, D. N., & Albers, H.E., 2022. CRISPR-Cas9 editing of the arginine-
617 vasopressin V1a receptor produces paradoxical changes in social behavior in Syrian hamsters. *Proc.*
618 *Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 119(19), e2121037119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2121037119>.
- 619 Terranova, J.I., Song, Z., Larkin, T.E., 2nd, Hardcastle, N., Norvelle, A., Riaz, A., & Albers, H.E., 2016.
620 Serotonin and arginine-vasopressin mediate sex differences in the regulation of dominance and
621 aggression by the social brain. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 113(46), 13233–13238.
622 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1610446113>.
- 623 Tidey, J.W., & Miczek, K.A., 1996. Social defeat stress selectively alters mesocorticolimbic dopamine release:
624 an in vivo microdialysis study. *Brain Res.* 721(1-2), 140–149. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-8993\(96\)00159-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-8993(96)00159-x).
- 625
626 Trainor, B.C., Pride, M.C., Villalon Landeros, R., Knoblauch, N.W., Takahashi, E.Y., Silva, A.L., & Crean, K.K.,
627 2011. Sex differences in social interaction behavior following social defeat stress in the monogamous
628 California mouse (*Peromyscus californicus*). *PloS one*. 6(2), e17405.
629 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0017405>.

- 630 Trainor, B.C., Takahashi, E.Y., Campi, K.L., Florez, S.A., Greenberg, G.D., Laman-Maharg, A., Laredo, S.A.,
631 Orr, V.N., Silva, A.L., & Steinman, M.Q., 2013. Sex differences in stress-induced social withdrawal:
632 independence from adult gonadal hormones and inhibition of female phenotype by corn cob bedding.
633 *Horm. Behav.* 63(3), 543–550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2013.01.011>.
- 634 Walker, S.L., Sud, N., Beyene, R., Palin, N., & Glasper, E.R., 2023. Paternal deprivation induces vigilance-
635 avoidant behavior and accompanies sex-specific alterations in stress reactivity and central
636 proinflammatory cytokine response in California mice (*Peromyscus californicus*). *Psychopharmacology*.
637 240(11), 2317–2334. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-023-06354-2>.
- 638 Williams, A.V., & Trainor, B.C., 2018. The impact of sex as a biological variable in the search for novel
639 antidepressants. *Front. Neuroendocrinol.*, 50, 107–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yfrne.2018.05.003>.
- 640 Williams, A.V., Duque-Wilckens, N., Ramos-Maciel, S., Campi, K.L., Bhela, S.K., Xu, C.K., Jackson, K., Chini,
641 B., Pesavento, P.A., & Trainor, B.C., 2020. Social approach and social vigilance are differentially
642 regulated by oxytocin receptors in the nucleus accumbens. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 45(9), 1423–
643 1430. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-020-0657-4>.
- 644 Winslow, J.T., Hastings, N., Carter, C.S., Harbaugh, C.R., & Insel, T.R., 1993. A role for central vasopressin in
645 pair bonding in monogamous prairie voles. *Nature*. 365(6446), 545–548.
646 <https://doi.org/10.1038/365545a0>.
- 647 Wright, E.C., Hostinar, C.E., Trainor, B.C., 2020. Anxious to see you: neuroendocrine mechanisms of social
648 vigilance and anxiety during adolescence. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 52, 2516–2529.
649 <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejn.14628>.
- 650 van Zuiden, M., Frijling, J.L., Nawijn, L., Koch, S.B.J., Goslings, J.C., Luitse, J.S., Biesheuvel, T.H., Honig, A.,
651 Veltman, D.J., & Olf, M., 2017. Intranasal oxytocin to prevent posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms:
652 A randomized controlled trial in emergency department patients. *Biol. Psychiatry*. 81(12), 1030–1040.
653 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2016.11.012>.
- 654
655
656
657
658
659
660
661
662
663
664
665
666
667
668
669
670
671
672
673
674
675
676
677
678
679
680
681
682
683

Figure 1: The CRISPR/Cas9 genome-editing system can selectively target the BNST and NAc in female California mice. (A) Schematic of AAV plasmids and CRISPR/Cas9 mechanism of action. (B) Experimental timeline. (C) Representative photomicrographs of viral spread in the BNST and NAc knockdown groups. Scale bar: 100 μ m. LV, lateral ventricle; ACO, anterior commissure; NAc, nucleus accumbens; BNST, bed nucleus of the stria terminalis.

B. Bed Nucleus of the Stria Terminalis

C. Nucleus Accumbens

D. Lateral Septum

Figure 2: Inhibition of *Oxtr* expression in female *Peromyscus californicus* in the extended amygdala and nucleus accumbens. (A) Representative images of CRISPR/Cas9 *Oxtr* manipulation in the BNST and NAc with OTR autoradiography. Control panels show regions quantified for NAc (blue), BNST (green) and LS (purple). (B) Control female mice compared to CRISPR-based knockdown of BNST and other treatment groups. Controls have significantly higher OBD than the BNST KD group ($P < 0.001$). (C) Control female mice compared to CRISPR-based knockdown of NAc and other treatment groups. Controls are significantly higher from the NAc KD group ($P < 0.001$). (D) Controls compared to all groups for density comparison in “control” region, the lateral septum. *** $P < 0.0001$ control vs. knockdown. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

706
707
708
709
710
711
712
713
714
715
716
717
718
719
720
721
722
723
724
725

Figure 3: Oxytocin receptor knockdown increases social approach and decreases vigilance after stress in the large arena test. (A) Schematic illustration of the Large Arena Social Interaction test. (B) Effects of OTR knockdown on social approach before and after social defeat stress (BNST KD n = 7, NAc KD n = 4, BNST + NAc KD, n = 4, Control n = 16). (C) Effects of OTR knockdown on social vigilance before and after social defeat stress (D) Representative heatmaps for the interaction phase showing reduced social approach determined by time spent in the interaction zone in controls but not other treatment groups. * P < 0.05, # p = 0.06 for BNST KD vs control, # p = 0.052 for BNST +NAc KD vs control, † pre- versus post-stress paired comparison. Drawings by Dr. Natalia Duque-Wilckens.

726
727
728
729
730
731
732
733
734
735
736
737
738
739
740
741
742
743
744
745
746
747
748
749
750
751
752
753
754
755
756

Figure 4: Correlational analysis of social approach and vigilance for controls and BNST KD. (A) OTR BNST density (OBD) compared to social approach behavior after stress. (B) OTR BNST density (OBD) compared to social vigilance behavior after stress. (C) Social approach compared to social vigilance after stress.

757
758
759
760
761
762
763
764
765
766
767
768
769
770
771
772
773
774
775
776
777
778
779
780
781
782
783
784
785
786
787
788
789
790
791
792
793
794
795
796
797
798

○ Control ○ BNST KD ○ NAc KD ● BNST+NAc KD

Figure 5: Large arena test open field and acclimation phase data. (A) Schematic illustration of the large arena test and the 3 phases: Open Field, Acclimation, and Interaction. (B) Open field locomotion activity for all treatment groups before and after stress (C) Open field center time plotted for all treatment groups before and after stress (D) Acclimation interaction time with an empty cage for all treatment groups before and after stress* P < 0.05 vs control.

799
800
801
802
803
804
805
806
807
808
809
810
811
812
813
814
815
816
817
818
819
820
821
822
823
824
825

826
827
828
829
830

Figure 6: Small arena test social behaviors before and after stress (A) Schematic illustration for the small arena test. Legend for treatment groups. Nose-to-nose sniffing (C), anogenital sniffing (D), social vigilance (E), lunging (F), and flipping (G) were scored with non-aggressive naïve target mice and then aggressive target mice. Tests were conducted once before social defeat and once after social defeat. † pre- versus post-stress paired comparison, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.